

Tracing the Low-Cost Carrier Business Model: A Bibliometric Research

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Abstract: As the low-cost carrier (LCC) business model has spread to markets around the world since its emergence, this issue has attracted scholars and a great deal of research has existed on LCC. This paper aims to present a general overview of the body of literature on LCC and identify past and present research trends. To achieve this objective, 853 publications retrieved from the Web of Science (WoS) database were analyzed in the period 1991 to 2020 by adopting the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-analyzed) methodology. Based on bibliometric analysis metrics, the most prolific authors, journals, institutions, and countries were identified. In addition, co-citation, co-occurrence, and co-authorship networks were generated by employing the Bibliometrix package in R statistical software. This study also provides trending topics and current research clusters.

Keywords: Low-Cost Carrier, Airline Industry, Bibliometrix, Bibliometric Analysis, Science Mapping.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of low-cost carrier (LCC), known as no-frills, originated in the USA in the 1960s and 1970s with Pacific Southwest Airlines and Southwest Airlines. After airline deregulation, it has proliferated in many local and regional markets across the world (Gross *et al.*, 2013). The LCC model, identified with principles such as simplicity, efficiency, and asset high utilization, largely dominates the domestic passenger markets today. LCCs typically serve point-to-point with a simplified fare structure. This model, which adopt a single-class cabin service with narrow seat pitches, mostly uses secondary airports. As another distinctive characteristic, LCCs use low turnaround time and rely on outsourcing to reduce costs (O'Connell & Williams, 2005). As such, LCCs have become an important player against the intense competition in the airline industry. The growth of the LCC business model has also attracted researchers and there has been a plethora of research focusing on this model in the last three decades.

Despite the growing interest in the LCC business model, analysis of the current status of the LCC literature is lacking. This issue justifies the motivation of the present paper. The purpose of this paper is to retrospectively analyze the growing body of LCC literature and to track past and present research trends. This makes sense because the development of academic disciplines depends on the contributions of individual studies, and these individual studies and topics are important measures for understanding research directions (Li *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, this study presents the academic literature related to the LCC model using bibliometric analysis. This approach involves the graphical mapping of the body of knowledge to gain deeper insights as well as presenting descriptive findings on the LCC literature (Martínez-López *et al.*, 2018). The remainder of this present paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 explains the methodology and elaborates on the processing of bibliometric material. Section 3 analyzes publication structure, productivity, and influence metrics and maps the bibliometric material. Finally, Section 4 presents the conclusions.

2. BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS AND MATERIAL

Bibliometrics implies analyzing bibliometric materials quantitatively, thus producing academic outcomes (Martínez-López *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, the most prolific actors in a field or journal can be identified and past and current research trends can be recognized. The main advantage of the bibliometric approach is that it allows retrospective evaluation at the journal or field level. As has been conducted in many other fields (Li *et al.*, 2017; Xie *et al.*, 2020), bibliometric analyzes have also been carried out in the aviation literature. Tian *et al.* (2018) examined carbon emissions in the transportation industry. Raza *et al.* (2020) bibliometrically analyzed revenue management in the airline industry. Bergiante *et al.* (2015) studied the relationship between air transport and business models. At the journal level, Tanrıverdi *et al.* (2020) examined the evolution of research in the Journal of Air Transport Management.

Bibliometric analysis includes two methods, namely evaluative and relational approaches. Evaluative analysis descriptively examines scientific production and influence issues at the individual, institutional, and country levels, while relational analysis requires graphical mapping of conceptual, intellectual, and social structures (Guzeller & Celiker, 2019). In a relational analysis, co-citation occurs when two documents receive a citation from the same third document. Co-occurrence analysis discovers the most commonly used terms in documents and focuses on the relationships between these terms. On the other hand, co-authorship analysis generates interaction networks between actors at the individual, institutional, and country levels (Raza *et al.*, 2020). These networks allow understanding which actors play an important role and the development of knowledge structure (Guzeller & Celiker, 2019).

The time span of this study is from 1991, when the first research was published, to September 2020. The research material was retrieved from the Web of Science (WoS) database, which is frequently used in the bibliometric analysis, applying the following advanced query:

- TS (Topic):("low cost airlines" OR "low cost airline" OR "low cost carrier" OR "low cost carriers" OR "no-frills airlines" OR "no-frills airline" OR "no-frills carrier")

Although 1098 records were identified after the first query, after the irrelevant sources and documents were discarded, the main analysis proceeded with 853 publications. We opted for the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-analyzed) diagram in the selection process of the documents to be included in the analysis (See Figure 1).

Source: own construction based on Moher *et al.* (Moher *et al.*, 2009)

On the other hand, the required analyzes on WoS data were conducted through the Bibliometrix tool. Bibliometrix is a package designed for quantitative research in scientometrics and bibliometrics on R

(an open-source programming language) (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017). For this study, the number of publications was used as the productivity metric, while the number of citations and *h*-index quantified the influence (Martínez-López *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, citation per year was used as another indicator of influence.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section provides a comprehensive analysis of the bibliometric material considered. Brief statistics covering the analysis of a total of 853 ($n=853$) publications are given in Table 1. Accordingly, the literature on LCC appears in a wide range of academic outlets ($n=261$). While 1333 authors have contributed to the LCC body of literature, 21.22% ($n=181$) of the publications are single-authored, while the remaining are 78.78% ($n=672$) the result of collaboration. In addition, the average citation per publication also shows that LCC studies are influential sources in the academic world ($M=15.83$).

Table 1. Brief statistics about data

Description	Results	Description	Results
Documents	853	Single-authored documents	181
Sources (journals, books, etc.)	261	Documents per author	0.64
Author's keywords	2020	Authors per document	1.56
Keywords Plus	1026		
Average citations per documents	15.83		
Authors	1333		
Authors of single-authored documents	143		
Authors of multi-authored documents	1190		

Source: own elaboration

Regarding scientific production, the body of knowledge on LCC has grown steadily. Figure 2 shows the total publications and the average number of citations by years. Regarding the total number of publications (TP), the number of documents published after 2003 increased gradually. The annual growth rate is also measured as 19.53%. In terms of average citation per publication, there is an erratic trend, where the period before 2000 was at its peak but recent years has a low average. This issue can be explained by the need for time to create citation potential for recent publications (Merigó *et al.*, 2019). This rate is likely to increase significantly in the coming years.

Figure 2. Annual scientific production over years

Source: own elaboration

Table 2 shows the most productive authors, institutions, and countries. It is observed that Redondi R contributed the most to the LCC literature with 24 publications. Following Redondi R, Malighetti P, Fu FW, Fageda X, Castillo-Manzano JI, and Dobruszkes F are other top contributors with more than 10 publications. Considering the author's influence, Dobruszkes F ranks first in terms of the total number of citations with 615 citations (TC). Considering the *h*-index, which indicates the number of *x*

publications of authors that exceeds the citation threshold of x , the authors' h -indexes do not fall below 7 and Fu FW takes the lead. In terms of institutional contribution, Cranfield University is the leading powerhouse ($n=39$), followed by The University of British Columbia ($n=31$), University of Bergamo ($n=23$), University of Barcelona ($n=21$), University of Girona ($n=18$), Loughborough University ($n=18$). Finally, the USA where the LCC business model is originated ranks first in terms of the number of publication. Moreover, it is observed that Anglophone countries dominate the first two places.

Table 2. *The most productive actors at different levels*

R	Authors	TP	TC	h -index	R	Institutions	TP	R	Countries	TP
1	Redondi R	24	305	10	1	Cranfield University	39	1	USA	220
2	Malighetti P	20	279	9	2	The University of British Columbia	31	2	UK	168
3	Fu XW	19	493	12	3	University of Bergamo	23	3	Spain	152
4	Fageda X	14	251	9	4	University of Barcelona	21	4	Italy	126
5	Castillo-Manzano JI	13	189	7	5	University of Girona	18	5	Australia	90
6	Dobruszkes F	13	615	10	6	Loughborough University	18	6	China	87

Note. TP denotes the total number of publications and TC the total number of citations.

Source: own elaboration

Journals in which peer-reviewed articles are published are usually worth examining as they reflect the quality of the articles (Li *et al.*, 2017). Table 3 depicts the top journals that contributed the most to the LCC body of literature. As seen in the table, Journal of Air Transport Management is by far the most contributing journal ($n=211$) in terms of both the number of publications and the number of citations. In addition, it is observed that the top 8 journals are specific to the transportation area. Considering the impact factor (IF) of the journals, LCC research has frequently appeared in influential journals whose impact factors do not fall below 1. Finally, according to Bradford's Law, which expresses how academic knowledge in a field is scattered across journals, Journal of Air Transport Management, Journal of Transport Geography, Transportation Research Part A-Policy and Practice are core sources in the LCC literature.

Table 3. *The most prolific journals*

R	Sources	TP	TC	IF
1	Journal of Air Transport Management	211	4748	2.811
2	Journal of Transport Geography	42	1235	3.834
3	Transportation Research Part A-Policy and Practice	30	563	3.992
4	Transportation Research Part E-Logistics and Transportation Review	30	775	4.690
5	Tourism Management	26	1129	7.432
6	Transport Policy	24	298	3.382
7	Research in Transportation Business and Management	18	125	2.189
8	Journal of Transport Economics and Policy	16	399	1.154

Source: own elaboration

In this section, the last part of the general overview presentation is to analyze the most cited publications, thus defining the most influential and popular studies. Table 4 presents the most cited publications between 1991 and 2020. Accordingly, the most frequently cited publication is "Market Structure and Multiple Equilibria in Airline Markets" by Ciliberto and Tamer (2009) with 187 citations. In the second and third ranks, the studies titled "Passengers' perceptions of low cost airlines and full service carriers: A case study involving Ryanair, Aer Lingus, Air Asia and Malaysia Airlines" by O'Connell and Williams (2005) and "Online purchasing tickets for low cost carriers: An application of the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) model" by Escobar-Rodríguez and Carvajal-Trujillo (2014) appears, respectively. In terms of average citations per year, Escobar-

Rodríguez and Carvajal-Trujillo (2014) is leading among 6 studies that exceed the threshold of 10 citations.

Table 4. *The most frequently cited publications*

R	Title	Author(s)	TC	TC per Year
1	Market Structure and Multiple Equilibria in Airline Markets	(Ciliberto & Tamer, 2009)	187	15.58
2	Passengers' perceptions of low cost airlines and full service carriers: A case study involving Ryanair, Aer Lingus, Air Asia and Malaysia Airlines	(O'Connell & Williams, 2005)	178	11.12
3	Online purchasing tickets for low cost carriers: An application of the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) model	(Escobar-Rodríguez & Carvajal-Trujillo, 2014)	166	23.71
4	An analysis of European low-cost airlines and their networks	(Dobruszkes, 2006)	158	10.53
5	The Impact of Low-Cost Carriers on Airport and Route Competition	(Dresner <i>et al.</i> , 1996)	150	6.00
6	The impact of strategic management and fleet planning on airline efficiency – A random effects Tobit model based on DEA efficiency scores	(Merkert & Hensher, 2011)	127	12.70
7	High-speed rail and air transport competition: Game engineering as tool for cost-benefit analysis	(Adler <i>et al.</i> , 2010)	122	11.09
8	Competition between network carriers and low-cost carriers—retreat battle or breakthrough to a new level of efficiency?	(Franke, 2004)	120	7.06

Source: own elaboration

This present study also mapped the conceptual, intellectual, and social structure of the LCC body of literature to provide deeper insights in addition to the evaluative results. As mentioned earlier, co-citation implies that the two documents refer to a third document (Tanrıverdi *et al.*, 2020). Author co-citation analysis was performed on 853 publications by employing Bibliometrix tool and presented in Figure 3. Among the 50 most cited publications, the most cited study in the LCC literature is O'Connell and Williams (2005), followed by Dobruszkes (2006) and Mason (2001). On the other hand, co-citation results reveal the existence of 4 different clusters. The largest citation cluster (#Cluster 4) consists of 19 authors, while the green cluster (#Cluster 3) consists of 14, the red cluster (#Cluster 1) 12, and the blue cluster (#Cluster 2) 5 authors. The main research themes that stand out in the related clusters are given in Table 5.

Table 5. *Research clusters of co-citation network*

Research Cluster	Research Themes
Cluster 1	Entry to LCC markets, pricing strategies, and competition
Cluster 2	LCCs and tourism demand relationship, economic impact/local development
Cluster 3	Customer perceptions and expectations, consumer behaviors in LCCs
Cluster 4	Airline business strategies and industry dynamics, competitive advantage, airport-airline relationship, airline networks

Source: own elaboration

Figure 3. Co-citation network of authors

Source: own elaboration

Keywords are a sort of summary of an academic publication, and the most frequently used words may reflect hotspots in a research field (Xie *et al.*, 2020). In this regard, this study examined keywords in different ways at different levels. Figure 4 presents common terms from LCC literature as word clouds. It highlights that the most frequently used words by authors are “competition” and “low cost carriers” with 118 occurrences. Apart from these, terms such as performance, demand, service quality have also frequently appeared in publications.

Figure 4. Word cloud related to research in low-cost airlines

Source: own elaboration

Keywords can also be a guide for identifying past and present trends in a journal or a field. Figure 5 presents trending topics for each year using the authors’ keywords. As the figure shows, airport competition, liberalization, and environment keywords were important in 2011-2012 while secondary airports and airline strategies were studied in 2007. Based on recent years, research specific to emerging markets such as China and India, and issues such as service quality and satisfaction come to the fore.

Figure 5. Trending topics in research of low-cost airlines

Source: own elaboration

In the keyword analysis, we lastly analyzed the co-occurrence of keywords to map the conceptual structure of the LCC research. Figure 6 shows the co-occurrence of the keywords of 853 publications recorded in the academic literature on LCC. Note that lines with the same color connect the most common term pairs in the same documents. Based on the results of the co-occurrence analysis, the most frequently used words represent 3 different clusters according to the relationships between them. One of the clusters explicitly covers marketing issues in LCC research, while the other clusters are established on competition, performance, networking and efficiency, deregulation, and tourism.

Figure 6. Co-occurrence of keyword network

Source: own elaboration

In the present study, we also generated co-authorship networks to reveal intellectual connections between actors (See Figure 7). As stated earlier, co-authorship networks refer to the level of collaboration at the author, institution, and country levels. In terms of author interactions, it is observed that collaboration networks are weak and there are relatively small independent research groups. The most frequent academic interaction has been established between Redondi R and Malighetti P. Considering the institutional connections, on the contrary, it is observed that larger-scale collaboration networks have been created. Accordingly, Cranfield University and The University of

the coming years. Cranfield University and The University of British Columbia dominate the literature on an institutional basis, while Redondi R and Malighetti P are leading in terms of the most prolific authors. Considering the contributing countries, the USA and the UK rank in first and second places. As mentioned earlier, the LCC research is available in numerous sources. According to Bradford's Law, we also found that the most core journals are Journal of Air Transport Management, Journal of Transport Geography, and Transportation Research Part A-Policy and Practice.

Based on the research results, we also examined the most influential, that is, the most cited publications. The most frequently cited paper is Ciliberto and Tamer (2009). Following these analyzes, network analyzes were also conducted to highlight complex relationships and provide deeper insights. At this point, co-citation analysis offers new insights. The result of the co-citation analysis indicates the existence of 4 different research clusters in terms of the cited references. These clusters cover many issues ranging from consumer behavior in LCCs to the relationship between LCCs and tourism demand. This study also identifies past and present trends in LCC literature. While secondary airports and airline strategies were frequently mentioned in publications in 2007, studies focusing on some developing airline markets and consumer-oriented issues such as service quality have come to the fore in recent years. Intellectual connections are another subject of network analysis. Accordingly, in this study, we mapped collaboration networks at the author, institutional, and country levels. While weak cooperation networks are observed for the authors, cooperation networks at the level of institutions and especially countries are getting stronger and serious interaction occurs around certain actors.

Although this study offers important insights into the body of knowledge on the LCC model, it includes some limitations. First, the analyzed material reaches the results based on the WoS database. It means that one should be noted that the results do not represent publications indexed in other repositories. Therefore, future research may develop a more comprehensive approach that also handles the publications in other indexes. Second, the visual analyzes available only on Bibliometrix were applied. It is obvious that additional analyzes such as citation burst will deepen the insights revealed on this issue. Despite the mentioned limitations, this present study is capable of providing a general picture of the academic literature on LCCs. Future research can perform bibliometric analysis on more sophisticated business model applications such as long-haul low-cost operations.

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